

EFFECT OF SNAKE VENOMS ON THE OXIDATION OF GLUCOSE AND ITS METABOLITES IN CELL SUSPENSIONS

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The effect of the venoms of a number of snakes, on the oxidation of glucose, lactic, pyruvic and succinic acids by pigeon brain suspension in the presence of air, has been investigated. It has been found that the oxidation of these substrates are inhibited to the extent of 82 to 90% by the venoms at as low a concentration as 0.033 mg./c. c. The effect of cobra venom on the anaerobic oxidation of glucose and succinic acid has also been investigated using Quastel's ferricyanide technique. These results show that cobra venom at a concentration of 0.033 mg./c. c. affects the succinic dehydrogenase only to a small extent. It has therefore been inferred that this venom even at low concentrations can strongly inhibit the activity of the cytochrome-cytochrome oxidase system.

It has been reported by Chain (*Quart. J. Exp. Physiol.*, 1937, 26, 299 ; 1938, 27, 49) that venoms of a number of snakes, when added in suitable doses, can strongly inhibit glycolysis in systems containing cell-free muscle extracts and fermentation in yeast maceration juice. He further states that the antifermenting principle of a venom can be neutralised by the corresponding antivenin. The effect of black tiger snake venom on a number of oxidases and dehydrogenases has also been investigated by him (*Biochem. J.*, 1939, 33, 407). From the results Chain concludes that only those dehydrogenases, which require a co-enzyme for their activation, are completely inhibited, while the others are affected either slightly or not at all. In this connection, experimental data have been recorded showing that co-enzyme I is destroyed, when it is incubated with black tiger snake venom for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours at 37°.

In view of the interesting observations mentioned above, it is worth investigating the effect of the venoms of some of the common species of poisonous snakes of India on the oxidation of glucose and its metabolites by tissue suspensions. The experiments of Chain (*loc. cit.*) and of Chain and Goldsworthy (*Quart. J. Exp. Physiol.*, 1938, 27, 375) have been carried out using cell-free extracts of muscles or enzyme preparation in which the tissues have been ground with sand and buffer solution, the fluid strained through muslin and finally centrifuged. In our experiments, suspensions of pigeon brain cells have been used as the source of the enzyme. This choice has been made in view of the fact, that the brain contains the most important nerve centres and some of the venoms used by us have got a paralysing effect on the nervous system. The results obtained differ in certain important respects from those obtained by Chain (*loc. cit.*). It has been observed by us that the oxidation of succinic acid, lactic acid and pyruvic acid and glucose are to the same extent inhibited by cobra venom at a low concentration. The oxidation of the substrates mentioned above is inhibited by about 90% by even 0.033 mg. of cobra venom per c.c. Since succinic dehydrogenase does not require a co-enzyme for its activation, the observed inhibition cannot be accounted for on the basis of the destruction of co-enzyme I. The alternatives which suggest themselves are that either the dehydrogenases involved in these reactions are affected or that the cytochrome-cytochrome oxidase system, which takes part in all these reactions, is inhibited by cobra venom. From the data recorded in this paper, the cytochrome-cytochrome oxidase system appears to be affected.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Estimation of the Toxicity of the Venoms.—The venoms of cobra, banded krait and Russell's viper were used in these experiments. Fresh solutions, in physiological saline containing known weights of dry venom, were prepared shortly before use. Pigeons weighing between 300 and 310 g. were selected as experimental animals. The minimum lethal doses were determined in the cases of cobra and banded krait venoms by intramuscular injections and in the case of Russell's viper venom by intravenous injection. By these methods, the minimum lethal doses have been found to be 0.1 mg. and 1.5 mg. for cobra and banded krait venoms respectively, and 0.01 mg. for Russell's viper venom.

Preparation of the Tissue.—The cerebrum and the cerebellum were taken out of the head of the pigeon immediately after its decapitation. The material was dried by pressing lightly with filter papers, cooled in a frigidaire for a few minutes, and then minced into a fine pasty mass.

Composition of the Medium.—The medium, in which the brain cells were suspended, consisted of phosphate-Ringer solution of p_H 7.3, prepared according to Peters *et al.* (*Biochem. J.*, 1933, 27, 842). The Ringer solution had the composition: NaCl, 0.9%; KCl, 0.025%; $CaCl_2$, 0.03% and $NaHCO_3$, 0.015%. To 786 c.c. of the Ringer solution 200 c.c. of 6.8% KH_2PO_4 solution were added and then 13.9 c.c. of 20% of NaOH solution to bring the p_H to 7.3. After allowing to stand for one day, the precipitate was removed by filtration.

Measurement of Oxygen Uptake.—The oxygen uptake was measured in the Warburg manometers at $37.5^\circ \pm 0.1$. The finely chopped brain (100 mg. portion) was placed into each of a number of Warburg flasks, broken up with a thin glass rod and suspended in the phosphate-Ringer solution of p_H 7.3. The desired amount of the venom, dissolved in phosphate-Ringer, was added to the brain where necessary. The substrate solution (0.2 c.c.) in phosphate-Ringer was kept in the side-tube of each flask, while 0.2 c.c. of phosphate-Ringer only was kept in the side-tubes of the controls. 20% KOH solution (0.2 c.c.) and a small roll of filter paper were carefully introduced into the inner cup of each. The total volume of the liquid in each flask was made up to 3.0 c.c. The flasks were attached to the manometers and finally shaken in a thermostat at $37.5^\circ \pm 0.1$ for a period of $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours, the system being filled with air. By this procedure much of the substrates in the brain cells was oxidised and the venom also exerted its full effect on the cells. After this period of shaking, the substrate was tipped off into the reaction mixture contained in the flasks, the level of the manometric fluid adjusted, and the stop-cocks of the manometers were closed. The oxygen uptake was measured at intervals of 15 minutes for a period of one hour. The results are expressed in terms of cubic millimeters of oxygen absorbed per hour by one gram of the moist tissue.

The data recorded in Table I show the effect of the venoms of cobra, banded krait and Russell's viper on the oxidation of glucose, while those in Table II show the effect of cobra venom alone on the oxidation of succinic, lactic and pyruvic acids in the presence of the pigeon brain cells.

TABLE I

The effect of different snake venoms on the oxidation of glucose
 Conc. of glucose in each case = 0.2%.

No. of expt.	Venom (mg./c.c. of suspension).	Cu. mm. of oxygen absorbed per g./hr. by				% Inhibition	
		Brain.	Brain + substrate.	Brain + substrate + venom.	Brain + venom.	Obs.	Mean.
Cobra.							
1	0.33	564	1150	204	160	90	91
2	"	234	765	129	74	89	
3	"	625	1042	190	161	93	
4	0.17	500	993	189	140	90	89
5	"	671	806	168	149	86	
6	"	705	1190	237	198	92	
7	0.033	494	905	123	87	88	87
8	"	559	1054	221	149	86	
9	"	369	856	145	87	88	
B. krait.							
10	0.033	480	840	166	130	90	86
11	"	520	950	233	160	83	
12	"	560	980	213	150	85	
13	0.0033	560	870	190	140	84	81
14	"	428	798	192	111	78	
15	"	340	762	170	92	82	
Russell's viper.							
16	0.033	530	780	120	90	88	89
17	"	470	780	115	84	90	
18	"	450	756	113	82	90	
19	0.0033	440	660	150	120	90	88
20	"	510	815	171	125	85	
21	"	425	835	159	110	88	

TABLE II

The effect of cobra venom on the oxidation of the sodium salts of the organic acids
 Conc. of the substrate = 0.033M in each case.

No. of expt.	Substrate used.	Venom (mg./c.c. of suspension).	Cu. mm. of oxygen absorbed per g./hr. by				% Inhibition	
			Brain.	Brain + substrate.	Brain + venom.	Brain + venom + substrate.	Obs.	Mean.
3	Sodium succinate	0.033	369	1166	87	200	85	89
		"	420	1240	110	192	90	
		"	262	1081	72	138	92	
4		0.067	439	1240	74	295	72	71
5		"	443	1079	181	372	70	
6	Sodium lactate	0.170	362	681	81	113	90	93
7	"	"	470	790	121	137	95	
8	"	"	292	600	70	85	95	

TABLE II (contd.)

No. of expt.	Substrate used.	Venom (mg./c. c. of suspension).	Cu. mm. of oxygen absorbed per g./hr. by				% Inhibition	
			Brain.	Brain + substrate.	Brain + venom.	Brain + venom + substrate.	Obs.	Mean.
9	Sodium lactate	0.033	380	700	92	130	88	
10		"	420	680	108	134	90	90
11		"	290	672	82	113	92	
12	Sodium pyruvate	0.330	344	744	87	103	96	
13		"	443	604	186	206	92	93
14		"	320	781	62	103	91	
15		0.170	406	1116	136	258	83	
16		"	406	1153	161	282	84	83
17		"	418	1090	149	271	82	
18		0.033	382	986	191	330	77	
19		"	420	1010	180	269	85	82
20		"	240	760	92	170	85	

From the data in Table I the oxidation of glucose appears to be strongly inhibited by the venoms of cobra, banded krait and Russell's viper. The data in Table II show that the oxidation of the succinic, lactic and pyruvic acids are also inhibited very strongly by cobra venom. These oxidations have been carried out in the presence of air. It is therefore worth investigating the action of cobra venom on the oxidation of some of these substrates under anaerobic conditions using Quastel's ferricyanide technique (*Biochem. J.*, 1938, **32**, 936).

Effect of Cobra Venom on the Anaerobic Oxidation of Glucose and Succinic Acid.—The principle underlying this method is that in presence of ferricyanide and bicarbonate, the hydrogen of the substrate molecule reduces one mole of ferricyanide and forms thereby one hydrogen ion, which then liberates one mole of CO₂ from the bicarbonate. Thus for each mole of ferricyanide reduced, one mole of CO₂ is evolved and this can be measured manometrically.

Approximately 100 mg. of finely minced brain tissue of the pigeon were weighed out in separate Warburg flasks and broken up in a Ringer bicarbonate solution of the following composition: NaCl, 0.15 M; KCl, 0.006 M; CaCl₂, 0.001 M and NaHCO₃, 0.025 M; 0.2 c.c. of a ferricyanide-bicarbonate solution, prepared by mixing 5 c.c. of 10% K₃FeCy₆ with 1 c.c. of 0.16M-NaHCO₃ solution. In the case of glucose, 0.1 c.c. of an 1% methylene blue solution was also added to the brain suspension. 0.6% Glucose (1 c.c.) or 1 c.c. of 0.1 M-sodium succinate in bicarbonate-Ringer was kept in the side-tubes of some of the flasks. The venom, dissolved in bicarbonate Ringer, was added to the brain suspension in a suitable dose. Necessary controls were kept. The flasks were attached to the manometers and the air displaced by a mixture of 95% N₂ and 5% CO₂. To ensure perfect anaerobiosis, sticks of yellow phosphorus were kept in the inner cup of each flask. The flasks were shaken in a thermostat at 37.5° ± 0.1 for ½ hour and then the substrates from the side-tubes were dropped into

the main compartment. The level of the liquid in the manometers was adjusted and the CO₂ evolution was measured for 1 hour at intervals of 15 minutes. The results are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

The effect of cobra venom on the anaerobic oxidation of glucose and succinic acid
The CO₂ evolution was measured after 1½ hours' incubation with venom.

No. of expt.	Substrate used.	Venom used (mg./c. c. of brain suspension).	Cu. mm. of CO ₂ evolved per g./hr. by				% Inhibition	
			Brain.	Brain + substrate.	Brain + venom. + substrate	Brain + venom.	Obs.	Mean.
1	Sodium succinate	0.033	240	1580	1250	340	32	
2	"	"	210	1100	910	260	28	29
3	"	"	260	1620	1340	340	27	
4	"	0.0033	250	1400	1560	310	—	—
5	"	"	160	910	1240	230	—	
6	Glucose	0.033	710	960	320	310	95	
7	"	"	650	930	310	300	96	96

It is evident from the data recorded in Table III that under anaerobic condition, the oxidation of glucose is inhibited to the extent of 96% by cobra venom at a concentration of 0.033 mg./c. c. In the case of succinic acid, however, the same concentration of the venom produces an inhibition of only about 29%. This shows that cobra venom affects succinic dehydrogenase only to a small extent.

DISCUSSION

An examination of the data recorded in the paper brings out the following facts.

The oxidation of glucose is inhibited to the extent of 86 to 89% by the venoms of cobra, banded krait and Russell's viper at a concentration of 0.033 mg./per c. c. Increase or decrease of concentration of the venoms by ten times of this value raises or lowers the inhibition only slightly, thereby indicating that the maximum effect the venoms can produce is practically reached at as low a concentration as 0.0033 mg.

Similarly cobra venom can also inhibit the oxidation of succinic, lactic and pyruvic acids to the extent of 82 to 90% at a concentration of 0.033 mg./c. c. The same concentration of cobra venom (*e.g.*, 0.033 mg./c. c.) thus brings about the same degree of inhibition, 82 to 90% in the case of glucose, lactic, pyruvic and succinic acids, although the first three of the substrates require a co-enzyme and the last one does not require any co-enzyme for the purpose of oxidation. This fact leads to the conclusion that of the various mediators involved in the process of transfer of hydrogen and its final oxidation by molecular oxygen, a particular one, which participates equally effectively in the oxidation of each of these substrates, is affected by cobra venom. It is well known that in the final stage of oxidation by molecular oxygen, the cytochrome-cytochrome oxidase system is involved. Cobra venom therefore seems to affect the cytochrome-cytochrome

oxidase system, thus bringing about the inhibition. This inference is further borne out by the fact that this venom affects succinic dehydrogenase only to a small extent which is quite insufficient to account for the total inhibition of 82 to 90% observed by us. It is to be clearly understood, however, that the possibility of the existence of a phosphatase in cobra venom, which can hydrolyse co-enzyme I, has not been denied by us. The point that we like to emphasise here, is that under the condition of our experiments, the cytochrome-cytochrome oxidase system is also affected by cobra venom and this alone can fully account for the observed inhibition.

C O N C L U S I O N

The oxidation of glucose by suspension of pigeon brain cells is strongly inhibited by the venoms of the cobra, banded krait and Russell's viper even at a low concentration.

Cobra venom has also a marked inhibiting effect on the oxidation of lactic, pyruvic and succinic acids by suspensions of pigeon brain cells in the presence of air.

The oxidation of succinic acid in presence of ferricyanide in an anaerobic atmosphere is affected by cobra venom only to a small extent. Under similar conditions, however, the oxidation of glucose is very strongly affected.

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